

WEIGHTED AVERAGE CHARGE FOR HETEROGENEOUS QUESTIONNAIRES AND WEIGHTED NETROPY

Abstract

In the present paper, we introduce the idea of "Weighted Average Charge for Heterogeneous Questionnaires" extending the Average Charge Studied by Duncan G. T. (1974). Some coding theorems and comparison results have been presented through weighted entropy. It is also shown that the Weighted Average Charge for Heterogeneous Questionnaires is bounded below by weighted entropy (Guisu, S.).

1. Introduction

Claude Picard (1965) laid down the foundation of questionnaire theory in his book 'Theorie de Questionnaires'. A medical doctor makes use of a diagnostic schedule, an electronics technician follows a trouble-shooting routine, a biologist designs a taxonomic key, the medical technologists economizes with a group testing program, a statistician presents a weighing design, the operation researcher devises a search scheme, the party goers seizes upon a "Twenty Questions" game strategy and indeed, sample surveyor mails out a questionnaire. Each of these procedures has a questionnaire interpretation.

Intutively, a questionnaire can be thought of a sequential pattern of questions perhaps heterogeneous in that questions vary in resolution. Since the use of a questionnaire presumably costs something. The charge would be spacificed but arbitrary, amount depending on the element identified and the questionnaire employed. Duncan developed the measure of average charge for heterogeneous questionnaire as follows :

$$E_p C(Q) = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} p_i n_{id} \log_2 d \quad \dots(1.1)$$

where p_i 's are probability vectors $\forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m p_i = 1, p_i \geq 0$$

n_{id} are the number of questions of resolution of d .

Duncan showed that (1.1) is bounded below by Shannon's entropy i.e.

$$E_p C(Q) \geq H(P). \quad \dots(1.2)$$

Sharm and Garg (1979) extended this work by defining a more general measure of average charge given by

$$E_p^\phi C(Q) = \phi^{-1} \left[\sum_{i=1}^m p_i \phi \left(\log_2 \prod_{d=1}^{\infty} d^{-n_{id}} \right) \right] \quad \dots(1.3)$$

where n_{id} is the number of questions of resolution d required to reach the state θ_i with probability p_i and ϕ is a continuous strictly increasing function such that ϕ^{-1} exists.

They characterized (1.3) in two different forms :

- (i) classical
- (ii) of order t by invoking the additivity property

and established that the average charge of order t is lower bounded by Renyi's entropy of order α , where $\alpha = (1+t)^{-1}$ i.e.

$$\frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log_2 \left[\sum_{i=1}^m p_i^\alpha \right] \leq \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log_2 \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^m p_i^\alpha \prod_{d=1}^{\infty} d^{(\alpha-1)n_{id}}}{\sum_{i=1}^m p_i^\alpha} \right] \quad \dots(1.4)$$

Again they considered non-additivity axiom viz.

$$E_{pu}^\phi C(Q) = E_p^\phi C(Q_1) + E_u^\phi C(Q_2) + \lambda E_p^\phi C(Q_1) E_{pu}^\phi C(Q_2) \quad \dots(1.5)$$

and the mean value property

$$E_p^\phi C_\phi(Q) = \phi^{-1} \left[\sum_{i=1}^m p_i \phi \left\{ C \left(\sum_{d=1}^{\infty} n_{id} \log_2 d \right) \right\} \right] \quad \dots(1.6)$$

where $C \left(\sum_{d=1}^{\infty} n_{id} \log_2 d \right)$ is a λ -non-additive function of random charge based on a $\log_2 d$ charging scheme and characterized the following non-additive measures of average charges

$$E_p^{(1,\beta)} C(Q) = (2^{1-\beta} - 1)^{-1} \left[2^{(1-\beta) \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} p_i n_{id} \log_2 d} - 1 \right], \quad \beta > 0, \beta \neq 1 \quad \dots(1.7)$$

and

$$\tilde{E}_p^{(0,\beta)} C(Q) = (2^{1-\beta} - 1)^{-1} \left[2^{(1-\beta) \frac{1}{t} \log_2 \sum_{i=1}^m p_i \prod_{d=1}^{\infty} d^{n_{id}}} - 1 \right], \quad \beta > 0, \beta \neq 1, t \neq 0. \quad \dots(1.8)$$

They showed that

- (i) $E_p^{(1,\beta)} C(Q) \geq H(P; 1, \beta)$
- (ii) $E_p^{(t,\beta)} C(Q) \geq H(P; \alpha, \beta)$

$$\text{i.e. } (2^{1-\beta} - 1)^{-1} \left[2^{(1-\beta) \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} p_i n_{id} \log_2 d} - 1 \right] \geq \frac{2^{(1-\beta) \sum_{i=1}^m p_i \log p_i} - 1}{2^{1-\beta} - 1} \quad \dots(1.9)$$

$$\text{and } (2^{1-\beta} - 1)^{-1} \left[2^{(1-\beta) \frac{1}{t} \log_2 \left[\sum_{i=1}^m p_i \prod_{d=1}^{\infty} d^{n_{id}} \right]} - 1 \right] \geq \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^m p_i^\alpha \right]^{\frac{\beta-1}{\alpha-1}} - 1}{2^{1-\beta} - 1} \quad \dots(1.10)$$

where

$$\alpha > 0, \beta > 0, \alpha \neq 1, \beta \neq 1, \alpha \neq \beta, \alpha = (1+t)^{-1}.$$

Guiasu, S. (1968) characterized "weighted entropy" axiomatically given by

$$H(P; U) = -k \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i \log p_i \quad \dots(1.11)$$

by considering an information scheme

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} E_1 & E_2 & \dots & E_m \\ p_1 & p_2 & \dots & p_m \\ u_1 & u_2 & \dots & u_m \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots(1.12)$$

where $u_i > 0$, non-negative real numbers corresponding to each

$$p_i \geq 0, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m.$$

Motivation For Weighted Average Charge In Questionnaire Theory

Bouchon (1976) considered that every element of E (a complete set of events) is characterized by a positive valuation and called it utility. This valuation allows us to give particular importance to every diagnostic obtained after a sequence of tests, to every operation described in a flow chart, to every result of a sort or - to every word of a given code, so it is quite natural to

consider the questionnaires which may be constructed using a weighted/utility quantity of information.

Secondly Kapur (1994) gave an alternative justification for the use of weighted measures considering these as functions of probabilities due to the fact to maximize or minimize or optimize. Ben Tal *et al.* (1989) obtained these entropic means by minimizing entropy like functions. They showed that weighted entropy and other weighted indices are needed for getting weighted means and this can provide a strong motivation for introducing these weighted measures of information or weighted measures of average charges for homogeneous or heterogeneous questionnaires.

Hence, we extend the studies further in questionnaire theory introducing "measures of weighted average charges for homogeneous/heterogeneous questionnaires". In the next section, we will study heterogeneous questionnaires defining new charging scheme and we characterize this "Weighted Average Charge for heterogeneous questionnaires" Section 3, presents a coding theorem for this new measure while section 4, presents the relation with Guiasu's weighted entropy.

SECTION 2

2. Characterization of $E_{(p,u)} C(Q)$

Let us consider the charging scheme

$$C.S. = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 & \theta_2 & \dots & \theta_m \\ n_{1d} & n_{2d} & \dots & n_{md} \\ p_1 & p_2 & \dots & p_m \\ u_1 & u_2 & \dots & u_m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Theta \\ N_d \\ P \\ U \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots(2.1)$$

where $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m$ are different states of a questionnaires of resolution d , $p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m$ are the corresponding probabilities, $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m$ are the utilities $n_{1d}, n_{2d}, \dots, n_{md}$ are the number of questions of resolution d .

Definition. We define the measure of weighted average charge for heterogeneous questionnaire Q satisfying (2.1) as :

$$E_{(p,u)} C(Q) = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} u_i p_i n_{id} \log_2 d. \quad \dots(2.2)$$

To characterize (2.2), we use the lemma.

Lemma 1. Let $\{c_i\}$ be the set of constants then $\exists$ a unique K satisfying

$$\sum_{i=1}^m (2^{c_i})^{-\frac{1}{K}} = 1 \quad \dots(2.3)$$

$$\text{and } KH(P; U) \leq \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i c_i \quad \dots(2.4)$$

$\forall$ probability vectors p_i , with equality if and only if

$$p_i = (2^{c_i})^{-\frac{1}{K}}, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m.$$

Proof. From (2.3) it is very clear that $K \neq 0$ but whenever $K \rightarrow \infty$ then (2.3) is satisfied for all $c_i, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. It is clear that $(2^{c_i})^{-\frac{1}{K}}$ is strictly monotonically increasing continuous function of K . Let X be a random variable taking the values $(2^{c_i})^{-\frac{1}{K}}/p_i$ with probabilities $p_i, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and K satisfying (2.3).

Using Jensen's inequality, we have from (2.3)

$$0 = \log \sum_{i=1}^m (2^{c_i})^{-\frac{1}{K}} = \log EX \geq E \log X$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^m p_i \log \frac{(2^{c_i})^{-\frac{1}{K}}}{p_i}$$

$$= -\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^m p_i c_i - \sum_{i=1}^m p_i \log p_i$$

$$\text{or } -\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i C - \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i \log p_i$$

$$\text{or } \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i c_i \geq K \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i \log p_i$$

$$\text{i.e. } \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i c_i \geq KH(P; U).$$

Now in the fashion of Duncan (1974), we can extend the idea for Guiasu's (1968) weighted entropy i.e. the weighted average charge for heterogeneous questionnaires Q is bounded below by weighted entropy, in the next theorem.

Theorem 2-1. Let the charging scheme (2.1) be satisfied. If Q is a valid heterogeneous questionnaire and $C(Q)$ is the random charge based on $\log d$ for each resolution d , then

$$H(P; U) \leq E_{(p,u)} C(Q) \quad \dots(2.5)$$

with equality if and only if

$$n_{id} = 0, \forall d > m \text{ and } p_i = \prod_{d=2}^m d^{-n_{id}} \quad \dots(2.6)$$

Proof. Let us define

$$q_i = \frac{\prod_{d=1}^m d^{-n_{id}}}{\sum_{i=1}^m \prod_{d=1}^{\infty} d^{-n_{id}}}$$

then we have

$$-\sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i \log q_i = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} n_{id} u_i p_i \log d. \quad \dots(2.7)$$

But refer Singh and Rajeev []

$$-\sum u_i p_i \log p_i \leq -\sum u_i p_i \log q_i = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} u_i p_i n_{id} \log d. \quad \dots(2.8)$$

Hence $H(P; U) \leq E_{(p,u)} C(Q)$.

If equality is obtained in (2.5) then

$$\log \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \prod_{d=1}^{\infty} d^{-n_{id}} \right) = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} d^{-1 \cdot n_{id}} = 1.$$

Hence theorem (2.1) establishes that Guiasu's weighted entropy is a lower bound for weighted average charge for heterogeneous questionnaire Q .

Corollary. Let the charge for a resolution d question be $C(d)$. Then

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=2}^m u_i p_i n_{id} C(d) \geq H(P; U)$$

with equality if $p_i = \sum_{d=2}^m d^{-n_{id}} \quad \dots(2.9)$

is equivalent to $C(d) = \log d$.

Proof. Let us consider any arbitrary positive integer d' greater than 2 then for

$$m = d' \text{ and } p_i = \frac{1}{d'} \\ H(P; U) = u \log d'.$$

Now $\exists$ a valid questionnaire with

$$n_{id} = \begin{cases} 1, & d = d' \\ 0, & d \neq d' \quad \forall i \end{cases}$$

$$\text{so } \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{d'=2}^d u_i p_i n_{id} C(d) = \sum_{i=1}^d \frac{u_i}{d'} C(d')$$

which must equal to $u_i \log d'$.

$$\text{Hence } C(d') = \log d'.$$

This result then establishes that the only charging scheme (2.1) for which K (identified in Lemma 1) is invariant over questionnaires in the $u \log d$ scheme.

SECTION 3

Definition. A weighted resolution d question is called a *Guiasu's efficient* if it is Shannon's efficient. So in terms of the above definition, we arrive at the following result.

Theorem. A Guiasu's weighted lower bound is attained by a valid questionnaire Q if and only if each question is *Guiasu's efficient*.

Proof. From Guiasu's weighted entropy, we have for a d -fold partition of Q with $Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_d$.

$$H(p; u) = H(q; u) + \sum_{i=1}^d q_i H(p^{(i)}; u^{(i)}) \quad \dots(3.1)$$

where $q = (Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_d)$ with $q_i = P(Q_i)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, d$) $p^{(i)}$ is the vector whose component gives the conditional probability—that the true state is the particular state of Q_i given that the true state is in Q_i .

We note that Q has sub-questionnaires Q^i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, d$ which resolve θ_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, d$) respectively. Also we have

$$E_{(p,u)} C(Q) = u \log d + \sum_{i=1}^d q_i E_{p^{(i)}, u^{(i)}} C(Q^i) \quad \dots(3.2)$$

By theorem 1, we have

$$H(p^{(i)}; u^{(i)}) \leq E_{(p^{(i)}, u^{(i)})} C(Q^i) \quad \dots(3.3)$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^d q_i H(p^{(i)}; u^{(i)}) \leq \sum_{i=1}^d q_i E_{(p^{(i)}, u^{(i)})} C(Q^i). \quad \dots(3.4)$$

Further, $H(p, u) \leq E_{(p,u)} C(Q)$ in which equality holds only when $H(q, u) = u \log d$ but this requires that $q_1 = q_2 = \dots = q_d$ i.e. the very first question of Q must be Shannon efficient $\Rightarrow$ it is Guiasu's efficient.

Proceeding in the same way, the same argument can be applied to the very first question in each of the state space of Θ . Hence it is shown that for equality to hold in (2.5) every question must be Guiasu's or Shannon efficient.

An iterative expansion of (3.2) shows that the converse is valid. i.e. if every question is Guiasu's efficient/Shannon efficient equality must hold in (2.5).

Duncan (1974) has shown that there exists a heterogeneous questionnaire whose average charge is strictly bounded above by the Shannon entropy plus 1 i.e.

$$\inf_Q E_p C(Q) < H(p) + 1. \quad \dots(3.5)$$

Analogously (3.5) can also be extended for weighted average charge scheme (2.1) as follows :

Theorem. Let (2.1) be satisfied for the state space Θ countable infinite. Then the weighted average charge for a valid questionnaire is never less than the countable Guiasu's weighted entropy. If the entropy is finite, then there exists a valid questionnaire with weighted average charge not greater than the weighted entropy plus 1 i.e.

$$H(p; u) \leq \inf_Q E_{(p,u)} C(Q) < H(p; u) + 1. \quad \dots(3.6)$$

Proof. Let us define

$$H^m(p; u) = - \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i \log p_i - \delta_m \log \delta_m \quad \dots(3.7)$$

where

$$\delta_m = \frac{u_{m+1} p_{m+1} + u_{m+2} p_{m+2}}{p_{m+1} + p_{m+2}}$$

we make that

$$H^m(p; u) \leq \inf_{Q_m} E_{(p,u)} C(Q_m) < H^m(p; u) + 1 \quad \dots(3.8)$$

where Q_m denotes any questionnaire determining the true state among

$$\{Q_1\}, \dots, \{Q_m\}, \{Q_{m+1}\}, \dots$$

Now

$$- \sum_{i=1}^m u_i p_i \log p_i \rightarrow H(p; u), \text{ (finite or } \infty)$$

as

$$m \rightarrow \infty$$

and

$$\delta_m \log \delta_m \rightarrow \text{as } m \rightarrow 0, \text{ so}$$

$$H_m(p, u) \rightarrow H(p, u) \text{ so } m \rightarrow \infty.$$

Case I. When $H(p; u)$ is finite, then taking limit as $m \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.8), we get

$$H(p, u) \leq \beta < H(p; u) + 1 \quad \dots(3.9)$$

where

$$\beta = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} E_{(p,u)} C(Q_m).$$

Now our objective is to establish the existence of a questionnaire resolution of Θ with a weighted charge arbitrary close to β . First we define

$$\delta_m^{(k)} = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{k-1} \delta_m \quad k = 1, 2, \dots \quad \dots(3.10)$$

and choose a positive integers $m^k, k = 1, 2, \dots$ such that

(i) $m = m^{(1)}$

(ii) $m^{(k)} < m^{(k+1)}$

(iii) $p_{m^{(k)+1}} + \dots + p_{m^{(k+1)}} \leq \delta_m^{(k)}$

(iv) $p_{m^{(k)+1}} + \dots + p_{m^{(k+1)+1}} \leq \delta_m^{(k)}$.

As we are dealing with finite sets in each case, we can let $Q^*, Q_{m^{(1)} m^{(2)}}, \dots, Q_{m^{(1)} m^{(2)}}, \dots$ be the best questionnaires for determining the true state among $\{Q_1, \dots, Q_{m^{(1)}}\}, \{Q_{m^{(1)+1}}, \dots, Q_{m^{(2)}}\}, \{Q_{m^{(2)+1}}, \dots, Q_{m^{(3)}}\}, \dots$ respectively, then Q_m^* can be extended to determine the true state in all of Q .

If we recognize this extended questionnaire $Q_{(m)}^*$, we note that the additional charge for $Q_{m_i}^*$ over Q_m^* is

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} q_k M_k + E_{(p,u)} C \left(Q_{m^{(k)} m^{(k+1)}}^* \right) \quad \dots(3.11)$$

where

$$q_k(m) = (p_{m^{(k)+1}} + \dots + p_{m^{(k+1)}}), k = 1, 2, \dots$$

Now we note that expression (3.11) can be no bigger than

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \delta_m^{(k)} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} q_k(m) \left\{ - \sum_{i=m^{(k)+1}}^{m^{(k+1)}} \frac{u_i p_i}{q_k(m)} \log \frac{p_i}{q_i(m)} \right\} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} q_k(m). \quad \dots(3.12)$$

This result follows from (3.5), (3.10). Then (3.8), (3.12) may be re-written as

$$\delta_m \left(1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{k-1} \right) + \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=m^{(k)+1}}^{m^{(k+1)}} u_i p_i \log \frac{p_i}{q_i(m)} \right)$$

which in turn equals to

$$5 \delta_m + \left(- \sum_{i=m}^{\infty} u_i p_i \log p_i \right) + \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=m^{(k)+1}^{m^{(k+1)}}} u_i p_i \log q_k(m) \right). \quad \dots(3.13)$$

Now as $m \rightarrow \infty$, the first term of (3.12) becomes zero while the second term must also go to zero since it is a tail of a convergent series $H(p, u)$ is assumed finite. Consider the third term of (3.13). Using Shannon's inequality, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=m^{(k)+1}^{m^{(k+1)}}} u_i \frac{p_i}{\delta_m} \log \frac{q_k(m)}{\delta_m} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=m^{(k)+1}^{m^{(k+1)}}} \frac{u_i p_i}{\delta_m} \log \frac{p_i}{\delta_m}$$

which is equivalent to

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=m^{(k)+1}^{m^{(k+1)}}} u_i p_i \log q_k(m) \leq \sum_{i=m}^{\infty} u_i p_i \log p_i$$

As entropy is finite therefore as $m \rightarrow \infty$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=m^{(k)+1}^{m^{(k+1)}}} u_i p_i \log q_k(m) \rightarrow 0.$$

Hence the existence of the positive integer m shows that the questionnaire $Q_{(m)}^*$ has weighted average charge arbitrary close to

$$\beta = \text{Lt}_{m \rightarrow \infty} \text{Inf}_{Q_m} E_{(p,u)} C(Q_m).$$

Hence $H(p; u) \leq \beta < H(p; u) + 1$ for finite case.

Case II. When $H(p; u)$ is finite, we have

$$H^m(p; u) \leq \text{Int}_{Q_m} E_{(p,u)} C(Q_m) < \text{Inf}_{Q_m} E_{(p,u)} C(Q)$$

where Q is any questionnaire to determine $Q \leftarrow Q$.

But $H^m(p; u) \uparrow H(p; u) = +\infty$ and so $\text{Inf}_Q E_{(p,u)} C(Q) = +\infty$.

SECTION 4

Particulars Cases

(i) When $\forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m, u_i = 1$

$$E_{(p,u)} C(Q) = E_p C(Q)$$

i.e.
$$\left[\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} u_i p_i n_{id} \log_2 d \right] = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} u_i n_{id} \log_2 d$$

 $a = 1.$

(ii) When $\forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m, u_i = 1$ the coding theorem

$$H(p; u) \leq E_{(p,u)} C(Q) < H(p; u) + 1$$

reduces to

$$H(p) \leq E_p C(Q) < H(p) + 1.$$

Remark I. When $E_{(p,u)} C(Q)$ is replaced by length of the codewords i.e. L_u , we have

$$H(p; u) \leq L_u < H(p; u) + 1$$

a coding theorem for useful entropy or weighted entropy Sharma Mohan and Mitter (1979) which again reduces to well known coding theorem when utility distribution is ignored i.e.

$$H(p) \leq L_u < H(p) + 1.$$

Remark II. These results again can be extended for various weighted entropies, divergence, inaccuracy and information improvement or J -divergence. Authors will extend this study further for order α , type β etc. in the next communication.

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